

Hydrogen distribution in electrochemically charged Ti thin film: High resolution SIMS analysis of electrolyte-exposed vs. electrolyte-free surfaces

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ABSTRACT

Understanding hydrogen-induced changes in thin films is crucial for applications in hydrogen production, storage, fuel cells, and protective coatings, whether to optimize hydrogen uptake or mitigate its detrimental effects. In this study, we employ a highly sensitive, in-house developed double-focusing magnetic sector Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometer (SIMS) integrated with a commercial Focused Ion Beam-Scanning Electron Microscope (FIB-SEM) to investigate hydrogen-induced transformations in electrochemically charged Ti thin films. We compare conventional immersive hydrogen charging, which exposes the film surface to electrolytes, with a novel backside hydrogen charging technique, which prevents contamination and preserves surface integrity. SIMS enables nanoscale visualization of hydrogen distribution, providing critical insights into hydrogen incorporation and phase transformations. This study underscores the advantages of backside hydrogen charging as a contamination-free hydrogen loading method and establishes SIMS as a powerful tool for analysing hydrogen behaviour in thin films, advancing the development of hydrogen-based technologies.

1. Introduction

With the increasing global demand for sustainable energy and the transition towards a hydrogen-based economy, the study of hydrogen interactions with materials have become critically important. Hydrogen-based technologies, ranging from hydrogen production, energy storage and fuel cells to hydrogen embrittlement studies in structural materials, require an in-depth understanding of distribution and behaviour of hydrogen at the nanoscale [1–4]. One of the prime candidates in these investigations are thin films, which play a pivotal role in hydrogen storage systems [5–7], catalytic applications [8], protective coatings [9, 10] and fuel cells [11]. Hydrogen's ability to profoundly alter the structural, mechanical, and chemical properties of these films makes understanding its distribution and uptake mechanisms essential for both optimizing performance and preventing deleterious effects such as embrittlement.

Owing to its low mass, high mobility and very low detection sensitivity, hydrogen detection using conventional microscopic techniques is

challenging [12]. Although methods such as the hydrogen microprint technique [13–15], silver decoration [12,16,17], scanning Kelvin probe force microscopy [18–20], and approaches based on hydrogen-chromic materials [21–23] have been employed to visualize local hydrogen distributions, they often lack the spatial resolution required to directly image the nanoscale distribution of hydrogen. Atom Probe Tomography (APT) can provide atomic-level lateral resolution for hydrogen mapping [24,25]. However, its application necessitates the preparation of needle-shaped specimens which would be challenging for thin films on a bulk substrate. Moreover, the limited analysis volume in APT may not adequately capture the overall heterogeneity introduced by hydrogen within the thin film. Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (SIMS) overcomes many of these limitations. SIMS is a highly sensitive chemical analysis technique [26] capable of detecting all masses even in trace concentrations [27], including light elements such as hydrogen [3,7] and lithium [28,29], with nanoscale lateral resolution. Unlike APT, SIMS can analyse larger areas without the need for specialized sample preparation, making it a more practical and effective approach for

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tracking hydrogen-induced changes in thin films. In SIMS, a focused primary ion beam (e.g., Ga^+ or Cs^+) bombards the sample surface, sputtering off atoms, molecules, and clusters. A fraction of these sputtered species is ionized (secondary ions) and directed into a mass spectrometer where they are analysed based on their mass to charge ratio [30]. SIMS can produce high-resolution two-dimensional chemical maps by scanning the beam across the surface. While quantification of SIMS intensities is not straight-forward, SIMS offers the benefits of high sensitivity and isotopic selectivity.

In this work, we present an efficient approach for visualizing hydrogen-induced changes in electrochemically hydrogen-charged thin films using a high-resolution Focused Ion Beam-Scanning Electron Microscope-SIMS (FIB-SEM-SIMS) instrument. This system integrates an in-house developed magnetic sector SIMS with a commercial FIB-SEM platform, enabling nanoscale chemical imaging with exceptional sensitivity. The capability of this instrument to map hydrogen distributions at the nanoscale has been previously demonstrated [3,7], and a detailed description of its design and technical specifications can be found elsewhere [31].

Electrochemical hydrogen charging is widely regarded as the most effective method for simulating real-world hydrogen ingress in materials exposed to corrosive environments [32,33]. Unlike gaseous hydrogen charging, which typically requires elevated temperatures and pressures, electrochemical charging allows for controlled hydrogen uptake under ambient conditions. However, one major limitation of this technique is the direct contact of the sample surface with the electrolyte [34], which can lead to unwanted etching, contamination, or even delamination of thin films during hydrogen loading. In SIMS analysis, such surface contamination and morphological irregularities pose significant challenges, as surface topographies can introduce preferential sputtering effects, leading to image artifacts that compromise the accuracy of hydrogen mapping.

To address these challenges, we explore a clean-surface analysis strategy for hydrogen mapping in thin films. We demonstrate our methodology using Ti thin films as an example. Among various materials, titanium (Ti) thin films are particularly suited for hydrogen-related studies due to their high hydrogen solubility and ability to form stable titanium hydrides (TiH_x), making them an ideal model system for investigating hydrogen diffusion, and phase transformations. By employing high-resolution SIMS, we investigate the hydrogen distribution in electrochemically charged Ti thin films, comparing conventional immersive electrochemical charging with an optimized backside hydrogen charging technique. The latter approach prevents direct exposure of the thin film surface to the electrolyte, thereby minimizing contamination and preserving the film's integrity for accurate analysis. To gain a comprehensive understanding of hydrogen-induced transformations, SIMS analysis is complemented with Laser Scanning Confocal Microscopy (LSCM) to assess surface morphology changes, SEM and X-ray Diffraction (XRD) to examine phase transformations. This multi-modal characterization approach provides critical insights into the advantages of backside electrochemical charging as a contamination-free hydrogenation technique, while also demonstrating the utility of SIMS in studying hydrogen distributions in thin films. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first demonstration of contamination-free backside hydrogen charging for nanoscale SIMS mapping of hydrogen in thin films.

Table 1

Chemical composition (wt%) of the 430 stainless steel.

Elements	C	Si	Mn	Ni	Cr	S	P	Fe
wt%	0.08	1.0	1.0	0.75	16.0–18.0	0.03	0.04	Balance

2. Experimental section

2.1. Sample preparation

A commercial AISI 430 ferritic stainless-steel rod procured from Steelinox BV, Numansdorp was used for both conventional and backside electrochemical hydrogen charging experiments. Table 1 outlines the chemical composition of the steel rod.

1 mm-thick circular discs were cut from the 30 mm diameter AISI 430 rod using an abrasive cutter and annealed at 1000 °C for 3 h in argon atmosphere, followed by furnace cooling. Both surfaces of the samples were wet ground using silicon carbide (SiC) foil up to 2000 grit. The top surfaces were further mirror polished using diamond suspensions and colloidal silica (OP-S). The samples were ultrasonically cleaned using ethanol. A 50 nm pure titanium thin film was deposited on the mirror-polished surface using an electron beam evaporator under high vacuum conditions (10^{-7} mbar) without substrate heating or pre-sputtering.

2.2. Experimental set-up

2.2.1. Conventional electrochemical hydrogen charging

One set of samples was hydrogenated by a conventional electrochemical charging method. Hydrogen was introduced into the sample using a two-electrode galvanostatic electrochemical cell, as shown in Fig. 1. The Ti-coated sample functioned as the working electrode (cathode), while a platinum grid (1 cm × 2.5 cm) served as the counter electrode (anode). A solution of 1 M NaOH with 1 g/L thiourea was used as electrolyte. Chronopotentiometry was performed at a current density of 0.2 mA/cm² for 180 min using a potentiostat (BioLogic SP-150). Upon applying the bias, hydrogen reduction occurred at the cathode, leading to the adsorption of atomic hydrogen at the surface (both at the thin film and the uncoated steel surface), followed by its diffusion into the sample. The sample was dried using nitrogen gas post hydrogen charging.

2.2.2. Backside electrochemical hydrogen charging

A second set of samples was hydrogenated using a custom-built backside electrochemical cell (Fig. 2). The setup included a stainless-steel base (anode), and a PEEK (polyether-ether- ketone) compartment

Fig. 1. Experimental set-up for conventional electrochemical hydrogen charging of Ti thin film.

Fig. 2. (a) Schematic of the backside electrochemical hydrogen charging cell. (b) Photograph of the assembled cell during hydrogen charging.

secured with steel screws, designed to hold approximately 600 μL of 1 M NaOH + 1 g/L thiourea electrolyte gelled with polyvinyl alcohol (PVA). The titanium-coated side of the 1 mm thick ferritic stainless steel sample faced outward, remaining unexposed to the electrolyte. The sample was positioned between the PEEK electrolyte compartment and a PEEK compression component to ensure a sealed configuration and consistent electrolyte contact with the backside. The contact area of the sample with the gelled electrolyte was approximately 0.785 cm^2 . Electrical connections were made via a brass connector for the cathode and a steel screw for the anode. Chronopotentiometry was carried out at 0.2 mA/ cm^2 for 360 min, which is double the time for conventional charging, to compensate for the additional time for hydrogen to diffuse through the stainless-steel substrate before reaching the Ti thin film. This configuration ensured hydrogenation of the thin film without direct electrolyte exposure, preserving the surface clean for subsequent analysis.

2.3. Surface analysis and characterisation

Hydrogen-induced microstructural and chemical changes in the Ti thin film, post electrochemical charging, were investigated using a hybrid FIB-SEM-SIMS instrument that integrates a FIB-SEM (Scios, Thermo Fisher Scientific) with an in-house developed magnetic sector SIMS. The FIB-SEM system consists of a vertically oriented electron column with a field emission source. It can be operated, among others, in Secondary Electron (SE) and Backscattered Electron (BSE) detection modes, with beam energy ranging between 0.2 keV and 30 keV. In this

study a beam energy of 5 keV–10 keV was used in combination with an Everhart–Thornley Detector (ETD) for SE imaging, while BSE imaging was performed at 10 keV using the in-lens detector. Imaging was performed with electron beam currents of 50 pA–100 pA. The FIB column, oriented at 52° with respect to the electron column axis, employs a $^{69}\text{Ga}^+$ liquid metal ion source (LMIS) with ion energies from 0.5 keV to 30 keV and beam current ranging from 1.5 pA to 65 nA. During SIMS analysis, the sample is tilted by 52° , ensuring normal primary ion beam incidence and normal secondary ion (SI) extraction, allowing a maximised extraction efficiency and hence maximised sensitivity of the SIMS measurements. In this study, SIMS measurements were performed at 30 keV beam energy with 50 pA–100 pA Ga^+ beam current. Fig. 3a illustrates the alignment of the sample during SE imaging (electron beam induced) and Fig. 3b illustrates the alignment of the sample during SIMS analysis (ion beam induced SE images can also be obtained in this configuration).

The SIMS system employs an insertable/retractable extraction optics box for normal SI extraction. The sample is biased at +500 V for the extraction of positive secondary ions (positive mode) and -500 V for negative secondary ions (negative mode). The extracted ions are analysed using a double focusing magnetic sector mass spectrometer, which offers a mass resolving power ($M/\Delta M$) of 400 and detects mass/charge ratios of up to 400 amu/q. The transmission of the instrument exceeds 40 %, and sub-20 nm lateral resolution can be achieved for 2D chemical imaging. It is equipped with a total ion count (TIC) detector for non-mass filtered SI detection in both modes (the TIC signal also

Fig. 3. Orientation of the sample during (a) electron beam imaging and, (b) SIMS imaging.

incorporates SE in the negative mode). For mass filtered SI detection, a continuous focal plane detector (FPD) [35] based on microchannel plates (MCP) and a delay line readout is used. This detection system simultaneously acquires a full mass spectrum for each pixel scanned across the sample surface. In this study, $^{48}\text{Ti}^+$, $^{23}\text{Na}^+$ and $^{56}\text{Fe}^+$ secondary ions from the thin film sample were mainly considered in the positive mode and $^1\text{H}^-$ and $^2\text{H}^-$ ions were the mainly considered peaks in the negative mode. The collected SIMS images were processed using ImageJ 1.54d software [36].

The instrument operates at high vacuum ($\sim 10^{-7}$ mbar), which can introduce background hydrogen signal due to residual water vapour in the chamber. However, in materials with sufficiently high hydrogen content, this background noise does not significantly affect imaging. To further improve the signal-to-background ratio, deuterium (^2H) charging was explored as an alternative to hydrogen (^1H) charging.

A Keyence VK-X1100 Laser Scanning Confocal Microscope (LSCM) was employed to investigate topographic variations on the surface of the Ti thin film after electrochemical hydrogen charging. LSCM enables high-resolution, non-contact surface imaging under ambient conditions, enabling faster analysis compared to localized probe-based techniques like Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) [7]. It allows rapid scanning over large fields of view with nanometre-scale height resolution, offering both qualitative and quantitative surface topography data. The system operates by raster-scanning a laser across the sample surface, collecting reflected light via an objective lens, with a confocal pinhole eliminating out-of-focus light to enhance axial resolution. A series of 2D optical sections captured along the Z-axis are compiled to generate 3D reconstructions of the film surface. These images were used to evaluate surface roughness, detect deformations, and quantify morphological changes through roughness parameters, providing insights into film degradation caused by hydrogen charging.

To confirm phase transformations after hydrogen charging, grazing incidence X-ray diffraction (GI-XRD) was performed using a PANalytical X'Pert Pro diffractometer. The system used a Cu anode X-ray source with $K\alpha_1$ (1.5406 Å) and $K\alpha_2$ (1.5444 Å) wavelengths, maintaining an intensity ratio of 0.5. Measurements were carried out at a fixed incidence angle of 0.3° , scanning 2θ from 20° to 80° in continuous mode with a 0.02° step size and 3.52 s/step acquisition speed.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Hydrogen diffusion in the sample

Ferritic stainless steel was selected as the substrate in this study due to its body-centered cubic (BCC) structure, which enables relatively high hydrogen diffusivity (10^{-9} to 10^{-11} m^2/s , around room temperature) [4, 37,38]. This allows rapid permeation of hydrogen through the substrate into the Ti thin film during backside hydrogen charging. Additionally, ferritic stainless steel has low hydrogen solubility, ensuring that hydrogen efficiently reaches the Ti coating without excessive retention within the steel matrix.

In contrast, pure titanium (α -Ti) exhibits a hexagonal close-packed (HCP) crystal structure, with significantly lower hydrogen diffusivity (10^{-14} to 10^{-17} m^2/s , under ambient conditions) [39–41]. Hydrogen in Group IV metals like Ti occupies tetrahedral interstitial sites. The solubility limit of hydrogen in α -Ti at room temperature ranges between 20 and 100 wppm [42], beyond which hydride formation is initiated. During backside electrochemical hydrogen charging, hydrogen initially dissolves into the Ti matrix as solid solution. When the solubility limit is reached, titanium hydrides (TiH_x) begin to form. The formation of specific hydride phases depends on the local hydrogen concentration, leading to the following phase transformations: face centered tetragonal γ - TiH_x for $x < 1.5$ and $c/a > 1$, face centered cubic δ - TiH_x for $1.5 < x < 1.99$ or face centered tetragonal ϵ - TiH_x for $x > 1.99$ and $c/a < 1$.

3.2. Conventional vs. backside hydrogen charging

3.2.1. Surface morphology and phase transformation

Both conventional and backside electrochemical hydrogen charging of the thin films were performed in a 1 M NaOH solution at a current density of $0.2 \text{ mA}/\text{cm}^2$. This optimal current density was chosen to minimize excessive oxygen bubble formation at the platinum anode, which could otherwise interfere with the hydrogen evolution reaction at the cathode. Additionally, higher current densities could induce solution heating problems, leading to undesirable thermal effects during the charging process [43].

To investigate the hydrogen-induced morphological changes and phase transformations, LSCM and electron microscopy were used for surface characterization. The obtained results revealed differences in surface topography and structural integrity, for each charging technique employed. In the case of conventional electrochemical hydrogen charging, LSCM height images (Fig. 4b) show a clear modification of the surface topography compared to the pristine thin film (Fig. 4a). The observed surface roughening may arise from one or a combination of factors, such as (i) degradation of Ti thin film from embrittlement due to hydrogen absorption or electrolyte etching, resulting in Ti islands dispersed on underlying stainless steel (ii) deposition or precipitation of ionic species from the NaOH electrolyte during or after the charging process. Fig. 4c further reveals severe structural deformations, including buckling, cracking, and delamination of the thin film. These observations strongly suggest the presence of internal stresses within the film. In conventional hydrogen charging, since Ti thin film surface comes in direct contact with the hydrogen supplying electrolyte, hydrogen absorption is immediate and concentrated at the surface. This can result in faster hydride formation, stress accumulation and mechanical failure, as observed. Furthermore, SE image (Fig. 4e) provides additional evidence of surface roughening and structural degradation, compared to pristine state (Fig. 4d), confirming the severe impact of electrolyte exposure during hydrogen charging.

These observations are consistent with findings by Duarte et al. [34], who demonstrated that front-side electrochemical hydrogen charging leads to significant surface degradation, including nano-scale blister-like features attributed to hydrogen-induced stress and cathodic corrosion. Similar effects of hydrogen charging on titanium surfaces, such as oxide film disruption, pitting, and passive layer exfoliation under alkaline and chloride-rich conditions, have also been reported in recent studies on Ti alloys [44,45]. These findings reinforce the susceptibility of thin films to cathodic delamination and roughening when exposed directly to aggressive electrolytic environments. However, most of these earlier studies were conducted on bulk materials, where post-charging surface damage can be mitigated by mechanical polishing prior to analysis. In contrast, thin films, due to their limited thickness, do not permit post-processing without compromising structural integrity. This makes the preservation of surface conditions critical for high-resolution analysis.

In contrast, the backside hydrogen charging technique, where the thin film was hydrogenated without direct electrolyte exposure, led to notably different surface characteristics. LSCM height imaging (Fig. 5c) revealed a subtle topographical modification, with a newly formed phase exhibiting a height variation in the range of 5–10 nm compared to the surrounding Ti thin film. This suggests that hydrogen incorporation in this sample occurred without significant structural deformation. Fig. 5a shows BSE image of the pristine thin film. Post hydrogen charging BSE image (Fig. 5b) confirmed the presence of this new phase, which appeared darker than the surrounding Ti thin film. In BSE imaging mode, the intensity is directly proportional to the average atomic number of the phases and so, the darker phases already suggest these areas to be titanium hydrides, as will be verified subsequently. Unlike the conventional electrochemical hydrogen charging, no visible buckling, delamination, or large-scale deformations were observed in the backside-charged thin film. This suggests that hydrogen-induced stress

Fig. 4. LSCM height maps of (a) the pristine Ti thin film, (b) thin film surface after conventional hydrogen charging, showing surface roughening (c) buckling, cracks, and delamination on conventionally charged thin film (d) SE image of the pristine Ti thin film (e) SE image of the Ti surface post conventional hydrogen charging.

Fig. 5. (a) BSE image of the pristine Ti thin film (b) BSE image of the backside hydrogen-charged Ti thin film, showing new phase formation (c) LSCM height map after backside hydrogen charging, revealing new phase formation.

effects were better controlled under this condition, likely due to stainless steel acting as a diffusion barrier slowing down the rate of hydrogen permeation into the thin film, ensuring more uniform hydrogen concentration, gradual hydride formation and thereby reduced localised stress.

To quantify these morphological variations, surface roughness parameters were extracted from the LSCM data. The average roughness (S_a), maximum peak to valley height (S_z) and texture aspect ratio (Str) (describes the uniformity and spatial distribution of surface roughness features) of the samples were compared. An Str value close to 0 indicates anisotropic or directional surface texture, while a value near 1 suggests isotropic, uniformly distributed roughness. The roughness measurements were averaged over ten randomly selected regions of $10 \mu\text{m} \times 10 \mu\text{m}$ on each sample. The pristine thin film exhibited low surface roughness ($S_a = 1.6 \text{ nm}$, $S_z = 13 \text{ nm}$ and $Str = 0.254$), indicating an initially smooth surface. Following conventional hydrogen charging the surface roughness increased approximately 30-fold ($S_a = 43.5 \text{ nm}$, $S_z = 413.8 \text{ nm}$ and $Str = 0.847$), indicating the severity of surface modifications introduced by direct electrolyte exposure. Buckled regions were intentionally excluded from these measurements due to their extreme deformation values. In contrast, backside hydrogen charging resulted in only a modest roughness increase ($S_a = 2.8 \text{ nm}$, $S_z = 19 \text{ nm}$, $Str = 0.375$), suggesting that the film maintained its integrity while undergoing hydrogenation.

3.2.2. XRD analysis

The GI-XRD analysis provided conclusive crystallographic evidence of hydrogen induced phase transformation in the backside hydrogen

charged Ti thin film. As shown in Fig. 6, the XRD pattern of the pristine sample exhibited peaks corresponding to HCP titanium (PDF 01-089-

Fig. 6. Grazing incidence XRD patterns of pure Ti (black) and backside hydrogen-charged Ti (red), recorded at a constant incident angle of 0.3° . The formation of $\text{TiH}_{1.99}$ hydride phases in the hydrogenated Ti thin film is evident, indicating formation of new phase in backside electrochemically charged thin film. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

4893; $P6_3/mmc$, α -Ti), which is the stable phase at room temperature, along with peaks from the underlying ferritic stainless steel substrate (PDF 04-003-5301; cubic Fe, $Im-3m$).

After backside electrochemical hydrogen charging, diffraction pattern showed peaks corresponding to titanium hydride ($TiH_{1.99}$), confirming the partial transformation of metallic titanium into cubic δ -hydride (PDF 04-023-9833; Cubic $TiH_{1.99}$, $Fm-3m$). The post-charging XRD results also revealed structural transformation of the titanium phase. The Ti peaks also displayed a change in symmetry, indicating a phase transition from HCP Ti to cubic Ti (PDF 00-044-1288; $Im-3m$). This is the result of hydrogen atoms occupying interstitial sites in the lattice, expanding the unit cell and altering its symmetry.

While the titanium film exhibited significant structural changes, the underlying ferritic stainless steel remained unaffected, indicating that hydrogen exposure predominantly affected the Ti layer without significantly altering the substrate. This suggests that the stainless-steel substrate maintained its stability under the applied charging conditions, reinforcing the idea that hydrogen-induced transformations were largely confined to the Ti film. The absence of additional peaks from unwanted oxidation or impurity phases indicates that the phase transformation occurred without significant contamination. Moreover, the Ti thin film was deposited under high vacuum conditions, which minimizes oxide formation at the Ti/ferritic stainless steel interface. This ensures a clean interface for hydrogen diffusion during backside charging. This further supports the effectiveness of the experimental approach in achieving controlled hydrogenation of the Ti thin film.

3.2.3. Chemical composition

To investigate the origin of surface topography variations following different hydrogen charging methods, SIMS analyses were performed on pristine, conventionally charged, and backside-charged Ti thin films. The mass spectra obtained in positive mode revealed that both the

pristine and backside hydrogen-charged thin films exhibited minimal contamination, indicating that these samples remained largely unaffected by external impurities. In contrast, the conventional hydrogen-charged sample showed a notable increase in sodium (Na^+) counts, suggesting the incorporation of sodium-based impurities during the hydrogen charging process. This observation strongly indicates that electrolyte components, particularly sodium ions from the NaOH solution, were deposited onto the sample surface during or after charging.

Post-charging SIMS images obtained for conventional hydrogen charged thin film (Fig. 7a) in positive mode confirmed a notable increase in Na^+ signal intensity distributed across the thin film surface and within the contaminant deposits. Within these deposits, the titanium (Ti^+) (Fig. 7b) signal intensity was relatively low, implying that the observed deposits originated from the precipitation of electrolyte components, rather than from the degradation or dissolution of the titanium film itself. Negative mode H^- SIMS images revealed an overall increase in hydrogen content post-charging (Fig. 7d) compared to the pristine film (Fig. 7c). Additionally, a localized increase in hydrogen intensity was observed along the boundaries of contaminant deposits, creating the impression of higher hydrogen accumulation in these regions. This increase in H^- signal intensity, however, is likely due to the edge effect in SIMS imaging which is a result of higher sputter yields at the edges or protrusions on the sample surface compared to flat regions. The presence of surface impurities in conventionally hydrogen charged thin films poses a significant challenge to the accurate mapping of hydrogen distribution using SIMS. The accumulation of contaminant deposits disrupts the homogeneity of the sputtering process, leading to preferential sputtering effects and non-uniform hydrogen detection across the surface.

Another potential factor affecting hydrogen detection using SIMS is the operating vacuum conditions of the instrument. As SIMS operates under high vacuum conditions, residual water vapour in the chamber

Fig. 7. (a) Na^+ SIMS image showing the distribution of sodium, indicating electrolyte contamination. (b) Ti^+ SIMS image displaying inverse contrast to sodium signal, wherein regions with low Ti signal correspond to the locations of sodium-rich contamination. Both the images were obtained in positive mode, post conventional electrochemical hydrogen charging. (c) H^- SIMS image of the thin film before hydrogen charging (d) H^- SIMS image of the sample after conventional hydrogen charging. The actual maximum H^- SIMS signal intensity in the post-hydrogen charging image exceeded the upper limit of the colour scale used here. For better visual comparison of the average hydrogen signal between the pristine and hydrogenated samples, both images were rescaled to the same maximum count value. As a result, edge regions in the hydrogenated sample appear oversaturated due to local signal enhancement from edge effect. H^- SIMS images were obtained in negative mode. All images were acquired over a $21 \mu m \times 21 \mu m$ field of view at a resolution of 256×256 pixels, using a 50 pA beam current and a dwell time of 1.5 ms per pixel. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

will deposit on the sample surface during analysis, contributing to the H signal. This introduces an additional ambiguity in distinguishing between hydrogen originating from electrochemical charging and hydrogen introduced during analysis. These artifacts in SIMS imaging have been reported in previous studies, where topography-induced signal variation and hydrogen background were shown to compromise SIMS accuracy [46–48]. Therefore, our conventional hydrogen charging results underline the importance of clean surfaces and controlled charging conditions for reliable hydrogen SIMS imaging.

In the case of backside hydrogen charging, SIMS analysis was conducted to directly visualize hydrogen distribution within the newly formed hydride phases. Fig. 8a shows H^- SIMS image of the pristine thin film. Despite the presence of a high background hydrogen signal, H^- SIMS images post backside hydrogen charging in negative mode revealed a clear increase in hydrogen signal intensity within the hydride phase compared to the surrounding matrix, as shown in Fig. 8b and 8c. However, the hydrogen signal within the matrix was still higher than in the pristine thin film. This is due to the contribution from hydrogen in solid solution within Ti matrix, which has not necessarily formed separate hydride phase.

High-resolution SIMS hydrogen mapping demonstrates the ability of SIMS to track hydrogen incorporation even at the nanoscale, highlighting its effectiveness in detecting nanometre-sized hydrides. Fig. 8b and c presents SIMS hydrogen maps from two distinct regions of the sample, each covering a $28 \mu\text{m} \times 28 \mu\text{m}$ field of view. These images reveal variations in hydride size and distribution, suggesting that hydride nucleation and growth are not uniform across the film. Such differences likely arise from localized variations in hydrogen diffusivity through the ferritic stainless-steel substrate, which influence the kinetics of hydride formation. Furthermore, in contrast to immersive hydrogen charging, no significant edge effects or preferential sputtering artifacts were observed in the SIMS images for backside hydrogen charging. This suggests that backside hydrogen charging provides a more uniform and reliable method for studying hydrogen distribution without the complications introduced by surface irregularities and contaminant accumulation. Additionally, repeating the experiment with deuterium

(Supplementary Section 1.1) confirms that the increased deuterium signal in the observed deuterides originates from electrochemically introduced deuterium. While a minor contribution from residual chamber water vapour cannot be entirely excluded in the case of hydrogen charged sample, the deuterium results support the conclusion that hydride formation is primarily driven by the applied charging process.

Our results are consistent with findings by Duarte et al. [34], who demonstrated that eliminating direct electrolyte contact mitigates surface damage and ensures more consistent mechanical data. Similarly, Kim and Tasan [49] highlighted the advantages of backside electrochemical setups for achieving clean surface conditions in SEM-based investigations. While these earlier studies have paved way to understand the benefits of backside hydrogen charging in terms of mechanical and microstructural properties in bulk materials, our work advances this concept by enabling direct, nanoscale visualization of hydrogen distribution in thin films using high-resolution SIMS. By combining a contamination-free charging approach with sensitive chemical imaging, our study provides a novel and powerful methodology for probing hydrogen-induced transformations in thin films. By extending this technique to real-time SIMS analysis during hydrogen charging, it may be possible to gain critical insights into localized hydrogen transport effects, phase transformation kinetics, and the role of microstructural heterogeneities in the formation and evolution of hydrides.

4. Conclusions

In this study, we have demonstrated SIMS analysis performed on a FIB-SEM platform as a powerful technique for obtaining highly lateral resolved hydrogen images, emphasizing the critical importance of a clean sample surface for reliable SIMS analysis. To achieve this, we developed and demonstrated backside electrochemical hydrogen charging as a better alternative to conventional method. Through a comparative study of conventional immersive and backside electrochemical hydrogen charging, we investigated the effects of controlled hydrogenation on a 50 nm Ti thin film and assessed the structural and

Fig. 8. Hydrogen (H^-) SIMS images of the backside hydrogen-charged Ti thin film: (a) Before hydrogen charging (b) & (c) After hydrogen charging, obtained from different regions of interest, revealing a significant increase in hydrogen intensity from the hydride phases and heterogeneous distribution of hydrides across the surface. All images were acquired with a field of view of $28 \times 28 \mu\text{m}$, at 256×256 -pixel resolution, and a dwell time of 3 ms per pixel (d) Mass spectrum for the sample showing a peak corresponding to $^1\text{H}^-$ at $m/z = 1$, but no peak at $m/z = 2$ corresponding to $^1\text{H}_2^-$.

chemical modifications using LSCM, electron microscopy, SIMS, and XRD.

In conventional electrochemical hydrogen charging, where hydrogen was directly introduced to the Ti thin film surface in an aqueous 1 M NaOH electrolyte, post-charging LSCM and SEM images revealed significant surface topographical variations, including thin film buckling, surface roughening, and contaminant deposition. SIMS analysis confirmed that these surface irregularities originated from electrolyte-derived precipitates and deposits, which hindered accurate hydrogen distribution mapping. Furthermore, hydrogen SIMS images exhibited elevated hydrogen signal intensities along the boundaries of the deposits, which can be attributed to the edge effect artefact, where enhanced sputtering occurs at surface protrusions, leading to misleading intensity variations.

In contrast, backside electrochemical hydrogen charging, performed using an in-house developed setup with a NaOH-PVA gel electrolyte, successfully eliminated surface contamination and structural deformations. Both LSCM and electron microscopy identified the formation of a new phase, which SIMS and XRD analyses confirmed to be titanium hydride (TiH_{1.99}). Unlike the immersed sample, hydrogen SIMS images of the backside-charged sample exhibited a notably uniform hydrogen signal intensity within the hydride phase, without any edge-effect artifacts or localized hydrogen intensification due to contamination. The backside charging method we have demonstrated in this work is particularly valuable to investigate hydrogenation effects in thin films.

Beyond ex-situ studies, this technique holds great potential for in-situ and operando applications, where real-time SIMS analysis can be integrated with electrochemical charging for tracking hydrogen diffusion, phase transformations, and hydrogen induced damages under dynamic conditions. This approach could be invaluable for hydrogen embrittlement studies, hydrogen storage systems, corrosion resistant coatings and fuel cell materials research, providing deeper insights into hydrogen behaviour in technologically relevant environments.

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The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2025.150290>.

Data availability

Raw data of the experimental results associated with this publication is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15791292>.

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